

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This is another slim issue of J.UCS: the summer time is showing! Nevertheless, its three excellent papers are well-worth looking at!

Now that summer is over we seem to be getting more good-quality submissions. Thanks to all our contributors and to our referees who volunteer to review them!

Concerning the modalities from 2000 onward I have no news from Springer yet, but I hope to be able to report concerning this matter next time.

Please enjoy reading this issue, and don't forget to look out for the two upcoming special issues!

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu